

A Literature Review of Servant Leadership and Criticism of Advanced Research

Authors : So-Jung Kim, Kyoung-Seok Kim, Yeong-Gyeong Choi

Abstract : Although there are many theories and discussion of leadership, the necessity of having a new leadership paradigm was emphasized. The existing leadership characteristic of instruction and control revealed its limitations. Market competition becomes fierce and economic recession never ends worldwide. Of the leadership theories, servant leadership was introduced recently and is in line with the environmental changes of the organization. Servant leadership is a combination of two words, 'servant' and 'leader' and can be defined as the role of the leader who focuses on doing voluntary work for others with altruistic ethics, makes members, customers, and local communities a priority, and makes a commitment to satisfying their needs. This leadership received attention as one field of leadership in the late 1990s and secured its legitimacy. This study discusses the existing research trends of leadership, the concept, behavior characteristics, and lower dimensions of servant leadership, compares servant leadership with the existing leadership researches and diagnoses if servant leadership is a useful concept for further leadership researches. Finally, this study criticizes the limitations in the existing researches on servant leadership.

Keywords : leadership philosophy, leadership theory, servant leadership, traditional leadership

Conference Title : ICIFE 2014 : International Conference on Information and Financial Engineering

Conference Location : Paris, France

Conference Dates : April 28-29, 2014